

A Process for Introducing Agent Technology into Space Missions

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Abstract—This paper discusses issues relating to introducing agent technology into satellite mission operations. Due to the high cost and long development time of satellite systems, scientist, commercial operators and the military are reluctant to use new and unproven technology, such as agent technology.

We are in the process of developing methods and processes for introducing agent-based systems into future satellite missions while both drastically reducing the risk of mission failures and gaining the confidence and support of mission management and PIs. We are doing this by designing and prototyping a robust mechanism to support dynamic agent-community evolution (e.g., agents adapting to community changes, agents joining a community or agents leaving a community). This dynamic capability of agents to join or leave a community or to adapt is necessary to achieve what we call “progressive autonomy.”

Progressive autonomy will allow us to gradually introduce autonomy and agent technology into missions and gain the confidence of PIs without having to commit to the technology from the start. It will also allow us to introduce mission management and autonomy into existing missions via ground station autonomy by working alongside existing ground station software.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Introducing new and revolutionary technology into a space mission is often met with resistance. From the view points of the Principal Investigator (PI) and the Mission Operations

manager, new technology adds risk to an already risky endeavor. A proven success rate for a technology is usually mandated. Agent technology, like other new and emerging technologies, will have an uphill battle for acceptance in operational spacecraft missions.

We are in the process of developing methods and processes for introducing agent-based systems into future satellite missions while both drastically reducing the risk of mission failures and gaining the confidence and support of mission management and PIs. We are doing this by designing and prototyping a robust mechanism to support dynamic agent-community evolution (e.g., agents joining a community, agents leaving a community and agents adapting to a changing community). This dynamic capability of agents to join or leave a community is necessary to achieve what we call “progressive autonomy.”

In our context, “progressive autonomy” refers to the level of autonomy that can be incrementally achieved by a dynamic community of agents. Achieving a higher-level of autonomy in a community means either increasing an already-existing agent’s capabilities or introducing a new agent into the community, which brings along with it a new capability or allowing an agent to develop a new or modified capability via a learning mechanism. It is this latter option that is the subject of this paper.

There are several reasons for wanting to achieve progressive autonomy. Two of these reasons are:

1. It allows a new capability to emerge from a community of agents supporting an operational mission after that capability has been verified and is trusted outside the operational environment.
2. A new capability may only be needed in a rare anomalous situation. In an emergency, a qualified agent can be dispatched to the community in need on a temporary basis. This keeps the operational resource requirements for the community to a minimum.

Figure 1 - Progressive autonomy of a spacecraft.

There are many issues associated with the concept of agents migrating to an agent-community to achieve progressive autonomy. Some of these issues are:

1. How is entry of an agent into a community effected? By transmission of the entire agent? By transmission of agent "DNA" for cloning in the community?
2. What sorts of credentials or guarantees are required by the community before a new agent is allowed entry into the community?
3. What strategies are there to integrate the new agent into the dynamic behavior of the community?
4. How are roles and responsibilities established for the new agent in the community?
5. How are any needed resources or privileges afforded the new agent in the community?
6. What role will "learning" play in the agent's assimilation into the community?

Thoughts on these and other issues affecting agent migration in support of progressive autonomy will be addressed in the paper.

Figure 1 illustrates some of the concepts that are associated with progressive autonomy in agent-based communities, on the ground and in space. The bottom part of the figure may represent an agent incubator. Here is where new domain specialist agents are developed and verified. This incubation period would involve the development of individual agents that are tested in a background or shadow mode. Then when confidence in its proper behavior is attained it is moved into an online community doing real work in its domain. It is at this level where the credentials of the agent come into being. These credentials attest to the development methodology and V&V that directly bear on the agents correct behaviors.

The upper part of Figure 1 depicts other communities that are purely operational. All of their agents are mature. An agent migrates from its initial community to other nodes in agent space (for lack of a better name). These communities are logically or physically distinct from the agent's initial community. Our major operational interest lies in a scenario where the initial community is part of a ground-based community of agents controlling a spacecraft and the community to which an agent migrates on-board the spacecraft (the top part of the graphic). It is while the agent gains operational experience in ground-based systems that its credentials begin to show correct and reliable behaviors in an operational environment.

In the remainder of this paper results from recent Goddard prototypes of agent communities, designed to support ground-based and space-based autonomous mission operations, will be presented. A general methodology for achieving progressive autonomy in space missions will be

discussed and the challenges associated with this methodology.

2. INTRODUCING AGENTS INTO COMMUNITIES

In our context, a community is a group of agents with a common purpose or goal.

In [3] the following were identified as requirements for a community of agents:

1. An agent community will have an overarching goal and shall accommodate subgoals.
2. Any two agents in the community can carry on a meaningful conversation. Thus, all agents in the community shall have a shared ontology.
3. An agent community shall have at least one user interface to entities outside the community.
4. An agent community shall have an infrastructure capable of supporting its internal communications.
5. An agent community infrastructure shall be capable of supporting the cooperative behavior of its members.
6. An agent community will be adaptable to environmental changes.
7. Agent community members will negotiate and share agreements.
8. An agent community will have integrated reasoning ability.
9. An agent community shall reason about at least one domain.
10. An agent community will be capable of negotiating their shared interests and individual goal priorities in several different subdomains.
11. An agent community shall have access to plans or partially completed plans.
12. An agent community will have a history-keeping and logging capability.

In view of our desire for supporting progressive autonomy within an agent-community context, we need a 13th and a 14th requirement:

13. An agent community shall have the infrastructure and mechanisms needed to admit or deny admittance to agents seeking entry.
14. An agent community shall have a community-leader agent (facilitator, manager, point-of-contact, etc.) whose responsibilities include keeping an accurate record of community members and their capabilities, and making decisions about potential new arrivals in the community. This requirement is in keeping with the current FIPA (Foundations of Intelligent Physical Agents) standards [1].

The level of autonomy of a system may be identified as the aggregate capabilities of the agent community providing the system's autonomy. The idea behind progressive autonomy

is that when a new or modified capability is needed to enhance a system's level of autonomy, an agent with that capability is introduced into the existing community that supports the system, or is allowed to evolve from an agent already in the community. Hence, introducing a new agent into an existing community is the agent adaptation or mechanism for achieving progressing autonomy.

3. CREDENTIALS FOR ADDING AGENTS

In our concept, introducing an agent into an existing community is not automatic. The proposed new agent must satisfy some admission requirements. These include a determination by the community that the agent's capabilities are in sync with the overall goals of the community and that the community's overall capability of achieving its goal will be enhanced as a result of the admission.

Additionally, the proposed new agent will need to have associated with it some certification indicating that it has been validated. Unvalidated agents will not be allowed to join an existing community. This will be discussed in the next section.

An agent's credentials may be represented in many ways but will contain information such as: list of capabilities, testing record per capability, and synopsis of operational history. Reviewing credentials and making decisions about admittance into the community is the responsibility of the community-leader agent referenced in the 14th requirement above.

4. INTEGRATING NEW BEHAVIOR

Integrating new behavior into a community of agents is highly dependent on the architecture of the community. Proposed agent communities usually consist of two topologies: 1) a collection of agents with a single agent or entity acting as a manager, broker or controlling agent; and 2) a community of agents without a controlling agent or entity where information is shared on a blackboard or broadcast out to the community at large.

The first type of community would be the easiest to add new behavior. Examples of these communities are the Lights Out Ground Operations System (LOGOS) and the Agent Concept Testbed (ACT) communities developed at NASA Goddard Space Flight Center [2]. The community of agents in each of these systems acts as surrogate controllers and interface with existing unintegrated software systems.

Figure 2 shows the architecture of the LOGOS community and Figure 3 shows the architecture of the ACT community. LOGOS consists of ten agents, some of which interface with outside entities, such as databases or scheduler, and those which are service agents. In LOGOS the controlling/managing agent is the System Management Agent (SysMMA). SysMMA keeps track of the agents that

are in the LOGOS community by requiring each agent to register with it when it joins the community. When an agent registers with SysMMA it would give its name, address on the network, and a list of its capabilities.

As agents in the LOGOS community need a capability they send a message to SysMMA and request the address of an agent with the desired capabilities. If SysMMA has an agent in its list, the address of the agent is sent back to the requesting agent. If an agent with the given capabilities does not exist, SysMMA returns a message saying that an agent with those capabilities is unavailable. SysMMA does not make any attempts to acquire a new agent with the requested capabilities.

On a limited resource system, such as a satellite, not all of the capabilities may be onboard. Due to limited resources, only a subset of the entire agent community may be present, with the others operating remotely on a server or other system, or being uploaded as needed. In a situation when an agent needs to be uploaded, a managing agent such as SysMMA would make a request to an outside server (or other entity) for an agent with the needed capability. In such a case, the original agent that requested the capability should be notified. This is because the needed capability may be time-critical and alternate actions may need to be planned if the new agent cannot be acquired within the needed timeframe. Resources may also have to be freed to load the new agent. The issue of resources is discussed further below.

The ACT system is another example of a community with a manager agent to coordinate the other agents in the community. In ACT there are spacecraft in orbit collecting magnetosphere data. The Ground Control Center (GCC) manager coordinates the agent community in the GCC. The rest of the community is made up of these agents:

- The Contact Manager Agent, which communicates with the spacecraft, sends and receives data, commands, and telemetry.
- The User Interface agent, which interfaces with the GCC and with mission scientists and operators.
- The GCC Planning/Scheduling Agent, which plans and schedules contacts with the spacecraft.
- Lastly, there are proxy agents for each spacecraft in orbit. These agents keep track of their assigned spacecraft's status, health and safety, etc. The agents flag the GCC Planning/Scheduling Agent when an emergency arises that may need re-planning.

Each of the above agents registers with the GCC manager agent. The GCC manager agent notifies them when a contact is approaching for their spacecraft; if another agent is going to be added to the community; and on how to contact another agent. The following is a spacecraft contact

Figure 2 - LOGOS architecture

scenario that illustrates how the agents work with the GCC manager agent:

- Agents register with the GCC Manager Agent at system startup.
- GCC Planner/Scheduler Agent communicates with the spacecraft Proxy Agents to get view data. It then creates a contact schedule for all orbiting spacecraft.
- GCC Manager Agent receives the schedule from the GCC Planner/Scheduler Agent.
- The GCC Manager Agent tells the Contact Manager Agent when and who the next contact is with.
- The Contact Manager Agent contacts the spacecraft at the appropriate time and downloads the telemetry. The Contact Manager Agent sends the telemetry to the appropriate spacecraft Proxy Agent for processing.
- The spacecraft Proxy Agent processes the telemetry data, updating the spacecraft's status, and evaluating any problems, warnings, etc.
- The spacecraft Proxy Agent sends any commands that need to be uploaded to the Contact Manager.
- If the spacecraft Proxy determines that a problem exists with the spacecraft and an extended or extra contact is needed, a message is sent to the GCC Planner/Scheduler Agent which will re-plan its contact schedule and redistribute it to the GCC Manager.
- The Contact Manager will download data and upload any commands from and to the spacecraft as instructed by the spacecraft Proxy Agent.

The Contact Manager agent ends the contact when scheduled.

For agent communities that do not have a central manager or controller, there is no single resource through which to request an agent with a given capability. In these communities, agents need to make known their capabilities by posting them on a shared blackboard (or similar device) or periodically broadcast them to the community. If an agent needs a capability that is currently not shown in its list of agents, it may broadcast a request for an agent with the needed capability to the other agents in the community. Depending on the protocol in use, if an agent with the capability exists, it may respond that it has the capability and is available or has the capability but is not currently available. In the latter case, the requesting agent can either wait or look outside of the community for the capability

In either managed or unmanaged agent communities, when an agent with a needed capability is unavailable, the requesting agent or manager agent has several alternatives, which include:

- The requesting agent can do without the needed capability or work around it if it is not a critical situation (this may also be necessary in critical situations where time is important and getting the needed capability would take too long).
- The agent can have additional choices with decreasing capabilities or use another capability that will also work but perhaps not with the needed speed or accuracy.
- The agent can request an agent with the capability from an outside entity. This could be from another

Figure 3 - Agent Concept Testbed (ACT) Agent Community

community, another computing resource (such as a host or monitoring system) or a person who then manually installs, locates or purchases the needed capability. In the future it may be possible to give the agents a budget to purchase or lease new agents with needed capabilities.

Because LOGOS was a closed system and capabilities were predefined, if an agent requested another agent with the predefined capabilities and it was unavailable, the needed agent probably had not yet been activated or went offline for some reason. In most cases, when a requested agent was unavailable, the agent developers had the requesting agent wait a predefined period of time and try again. If after repeated attempts the needed agent was still not available an error was issued to the operator who was suppose to manually start or restart the requested agent.

Depending on the autonomy of the agent community, other aspects also need to be considered when adding additional agents. These include:

- Available resources (see below).

- How long the agent will stay (temporarily until the task is completed or as a permanent addition)?
- Will it also be of use to other agents?
- What communication language does it use?
- Is it compatible with the community in other regards (e.g., goals)?

Each community will also have its own unique constraints that will need to be considered when adding a new agent.

5. ESTABLISHING ROLES AND RESPONSIBILITIES

When a new agent joins a community the community-leader agent is responsible for registering the agent and listing the agent's capabilities. This information will be used by the community-leader and other agents in the community in assigning tasks to the new agent.

The role of an agent in a community is a function of its own capabilities and its knowledge of access to, and application of the capabilities of other agents in the community. Therefore, the agent may need to also query the community-leader to find out the capabilities and needs of other agents

so that it can update its community model and model of itself.

The agent was probably added to the community to fill a particular need or replace another existing, outdated agent. If an agent was added to fill a need in the community, then the requesting agent(s) need to be informed by the community-leader that the new agent is now available. If it is replacing an existing agent, then the rest of the community needs to be informed that a new agent is available to replace the old agent, in whole or in part.

If an agent is being completely replaced and resources are available, the old agent may need to be kept for a burn-in period. During this time, agents can get results from the old and new agent to determine if the new agent is acceptable. If it is not, a request for another agent may be made with the new agent being removed or perhaps kept until the next agent arrives.

Keeping the old agent around while the new agent is evaluated is also part of the progressive autonomy approach to introducing new agents. The new agent runs as a duplicate to the old agent until confidence in it is gained. In applications where there are limited resources, the new agent can be run in a shadow mode on a remote server or simulator until confidence in it has been gained.

With current technology, when a new agent is added to a community its developer has specifically written the agent to fill a particular need. In the future when off-the-shelf agents become available it will become more important to fit the new agent into the community through a trial basis and then redistribute responsibilities for tasks based on the task set brought by the new agent.

6. ASSIGNING RESOURCES

In a limit resource environment such as spacecraft, assigning resources is very important. Examples of resources that need to be assigned are processor and memory resources, communication resources, instrument resources, subsystem resources and other resources that are domain dependent.

In agent systems, memory and processor resources are especially important. Due to weight and availability of radiation hardened processors and memory, the processing power of spacecraft are limited. Because of these limitations, adding new resources, such as an agent, may mean removing another resource, such as another existing agent.

When an agent migrates or an existing agent clones to a community with limited resources, several questions must be answered before the operation is performed:

- Are there enough resources available for the new agent? If not, which agent will have to be removed to make

room for the new agent and what impact will this have on the other agents in the community as well on the operations of the satellite or other domain.

- If there are enough resources, will the reduction in resources have an effect on the operations of the community in the future? If so, the prioritization of the current resources is to be reexamined or redistributed.
- How long will the agent remain in the community? If it is for a short time, to solve a specialized problem or to do an analysis of a particular situation, then other functions that are normally critical could be temporarily removed, taken offline or scaled back (depending on how critical they are) until the new agent performs its task. If the agent will need to stay in the community for a longer period of time, then resources need to be examined more closely by the manager agent, the community, and by the party responsible for initiating the migration.
- Will the migration make other exiting agents obsolete? If so, new resources may be gained by adding the new agent, which may also affect how other remaining agents can do their work (the remaining agents may have more resources to work with).
- How will the speed of processing and prioritization of tasks be affected by the addition of the new agent? Will the addition of the agent slow the community down, or speed up the community and how will that change the way work is currently being done? Adding a new agent can increase speed through parallel processing, but at the same time may reduce available memory and speed in other areas.

Depending on the domain, many other questions may also need to be asked. After gaining experience, many questions could be inserted into the reasoning component, which may be part of a manager agent. Many questions will be valid across communities and could be reused between implementations.

In some domains, updating or adding resources may be a possibility, while in others it may be impossible. In those domains where it is impossible, and where there are distributed resources, the manager agent may have to reassign processors and other resources as loads and responsibilities of agents change. An example of this may be on a mapping satellite with multiple instruments. The use of one instrument may preclude the use of a second instrument. In such cases, the resources for the agents of the second instrument can be scaled back and perhaps the agents can be temporarily removed.

Managing resources for communities is very dependent on the domain to which the agents are being applied. For most communities, constraints exist between agents and the available resources that ensure proper operation. Adding agents to the community necessitates examining these constraints to see if any would be broken-and if they are

broken, what would be the lowest cost in reestablishing the constraints.

7. LEARNING AND ASSIMILATION

Learning can play a crucial role in assimilating new agents into a community. The more ability an agent has to learn, the less customizing needs to be done to an agent to insert it into a community. Agents entering the community need to learn about other agents in the community and how to best utilize them, how to interface with a manager agent if it exists, how to adapt to a changing community and how to increase its own performance.

As discussed earlier, learning can be used in training the agent. If replacing a manual process, the agent can watch and learn how a person responds to a situation, and what actions that person takes when given a set of inputs. After the agent learns a sufficient amount, it can be put in a shadow mode to the human to see if its actions correspond to the humans. If not, the agent can be corrected. When the agent has learned enough to operate on its own, it can take over the operations of the human with the human okaying its actions. The last step would be when the agent replaces the human and only notifies the human when it cannot solve a problem.

The same scenario can also be used with a spacecraft simulator. An agent can be learning from simulated instrument or subsystem data instead of live feeds. When confidence in the agent is gained, it could then be inserted into the community or put in shadow mode, as in above, on the live feed.

8. CONCLUSION

Introducing agent technology into new and current space flight missions is gaining acceptance, but many PIs and others are reluctant to add new technology, which they view as high risk. Using progressive autonomy allows agent technology to be gradually introduced to a new or existing system. In this way, PIs and mission management can gain confidence in the technology and see the benefits it can provide without fully committing to the technology. This paper has attempted to identify some of the issues that need to be addressed to realize a robust approach to progressive autonomy.

REFERENCES

[1] Foundation for Intelligent Physical Agents (FIPA). FIPA Specification Part 2: Agent Communication Language. Geneva, Switzerland. November 28, 1997.

[2] Truszkowski, W., Hallock, H. Agent Technology from a NASA Perspective. *CIA-99, Third International Workshop on Cooperative Information Agents*, Springer-Verlag, Uppsala, Sweden, 31 July – 2 August 1999.

[3] Truszkowski, W., Karlin, J., "A Cybernetic Approach to the Modeling of Agent Communities", *Cooperative Information Agents IV*, Springer Lecture Notes in Artificial Intelligence 1860, Boston MA, July, 2000.

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